

REBOOT

EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Three informative videos and immersive scenarios

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT
Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
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CONTENT

1	Projekt Summary	5
2	Deliverable Abstracts	6
3	Deliverable Context.....	8
3.1	Artist in production	8
3.2	Artist in research	9
4	Deliverable interpretation / contextualisation in the Reboot project	10
4.1	Immersion, interactivity, multi-sensory and mixed realities as factors in the current development and innovation of cinematography: what does the production of 3 immersive videos and scenarios by Sara Tirelli demonstrate to us?	10
4.2	The immersive dynamics of innovation in modern and contemporary cinema	10
4.3	The immersive dynamics of innovation in contemporary art	13
5	Deliverable Description	15
5.1	„43° 43' 23.7972" / 7° 21' 32.3022", VR 360 video, 4K, 5' 15", 2024.....	15
5.2	“LOOKING FOR AGNÈS”, VR 360 video, 5K, 4' 13”, 2024	17
5.3	“FATHOMING”, VR 360 video, 2'47”, 2024	19
6	Aesthetic and technical interpretation of the delivery.....	21
6.1	Ascension	22
6.2	Remediation	23
6.3	“Looking for Agnès” additional interpretation	24
6.4	Diving.....	29
6.5	Student production n°1 – “Château de la Napoule / Napoule Art Foundation”	31
6.6	Student production n°2 – “Two parallel scenes with reciprocal causality of action”	32
7	References	35

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1 PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect the existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of 'measuring' 'analysing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. On the other hand, the project aspires to place attention to the active preparation for the future in the area of audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only the 'what is' but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' with fresh lenses. REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

2 DELIVERABLE ABSTRACTS

As part of WP7 “D7.8 Three informative videos and immersive scenarios (Media DEC)”, the role of the UCA research team is to deepen and explore the complex relationships between cinema and technologies of immersive communication. If WP5.3.1 studies the cognitive abilities of the contemporary spectator, by highlighting the existing differences between the creative public accustomed to the culture of Mixed Reality technologies and the non-creative public, the aim of D7.8 is to study the creative process in the immersive media sector and to understand how it contributes to the education of young professionals of actual cinematography increasingly oriented towards a mix of supports and media, as evidenced by the two recent extensions of the two largest film festivals "Mostra - Immersive section" and "Cannes - Immersive Competition".

As part of these goals, Sara Tirelli, an Italian artist known in the world of immersive cinema, undertook an approach that was both, creative and educational.

On the one hand, she worked on the theme of spatiality, an essential pole of her aesthetic interests, by highlighting the capabilities of immersive capture equipment, in this case the Insta Pro 2 stereoscopic 360° camera and the Zoom H3-VR ambisonic microphone.

On the other hand, she has developed a creative collaboration with the students of the ICCD Master, in a series of visits, masterclasses and collaborations by integrating into her artistic research students and teachers from the audiovisual sector of the Georges Méliès campus in Cannes (November 2023, March 7, 2024, February 26 – March 27, 2024, April, May 2024).

Sara Tirelli was also an active member of the Reboot research team at the University of Côte d'Azur by participating in meetings of researchers involved in WPs falling within the competences of this University. In this, she integrated the scientific objectives and partial results of our team.

The result of its creation will be broadcasted as a dissemination of the REBOOT project, among other things through participation in festivals and exhibitions specialized in Mixed Reality, and it will also be used as an educational support, both from an artistic and technological point of view, by future classes of ICCD Master students.

Reflections around narrative means in Mixed Reality initiated, among others, by the creative process of Sara Tirelli, allowed their implementation into practice by student creations. Two achievements will be presented at the end of this report.

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3 DELIVERABLE CONTEXT

3.1 Artist in production

Three videos and immersive scenario by Sara Tirelli.

To watch in the Virtual Reality headset. If you are viewing on the computer's flat screen, please set the quality to higher (1080s ^{HD} or 2160s ^{4K}).

Links to the videos:

“43° 43' 23.7972” / 7° 21' 32.3022” - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OZSWJb-5TQg>

“LOOKING FOR AGNÈS” - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ECqFTijFxxE>

“FATHOMING” - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=acmC3UIH-fg>

These three works, as part of a whole commission for the Reboot project, represent the result of the artist's experimentation in the field of immersive moving images and are to be considered prototypes exclusively for supporting academic research.

For any other use of the video, it's compulsory to contact the artist.

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Link to download the videos:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1CkfzdV6bclZ6hGNhZiSjFxyioUpC4T5C>

3.2 Artist in research

The three immersive films presented in support of the HORIZON 2022 Reboot research project are an artistic exploration of the spatialisation of the gaze imposed by immersive moving images. These works chart an ideal path through the Côte d'Azur: starting from Mont Baside, along the coastline, to the depths of the sea. The locations do not merely serve here as backdrops but define the coordinates of an image that becomes an environment. The gaze traversing these three films follows a vertical trajectory, from above to below, questioning the corporeality of the act of seeing and framing reality through the new paradigms of storytelling, aesthetics, and techniques of digital and immersive media.

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4 DELIVERABLE INTERPRETATION / CONTEXTUALISATION IN THE REBOOT PROJECT

4.1 Immersion, interactivity, multi-sensory and mixed realities as factors in the current development and innovation of cinematography: what does the production of 3 immersive videos and scenarios by Sara Tirelli demonstrate to us?

The place of immersive works, in particular the “3 immersive videos/scenarios” produced by the team of the University of Côte d'Azur with the artist Sara Tirelli as part of the European research project Reboot, can be interpreted in different ways than we can divide into two groups: interpretation starting from the cinematographic field itself, interpretation starting from the field of contemporary art, interpretations which converge in the current trend of new media in the broad sense.

To understand this double interdependence, it is therefore a question of grasping the elements of the specific dynamics of current cinema which displays a certain propensity for the production and distribution of immersive works with mixed and extended reality and the elements of the dynamics of contemporary art which offers a significant number of works using immersive techniques, by following the recent trends in the media sector where immersion and mixed reality is becoming the standard of the most used solutions.

4.2 The immersive dynamics of innovation in modern and contemporary cinema

The phenomenon of using the technologies of spherical capture, spatialized sound, multi-sensory, interactivity and the mixture of realities: that resulting from the photorealistic image with real capture, that resulting from the image of synthesis at different degrees of sensory immersion and that

resulting from the iconic frame of reference with natural perception, has been observed in cinema for decades.

Starting with the precursors of the 1060s/1970s, Morton Leonard Heilig (Morton, L., H., 1992), John Whitney (Whitney, J., 1991) and Ivan Sutherland (Sutherland, I., E., 1968), from the end of the 1970s, experimental cinema and video with their emblematic personality representatives Nam June Paik (Zurbrugg, N., & Paik, NJ 1990), Bill Viola (Keith, C., 1998 or even Bruce Nauman (Lewallen, C., & Bowen, D., 2019), constantly resort to concepts pushing the boundaries of classic cinema, both on the side of artistic production (screenwriting and capture/recording) and on the side of s viewing/hearing devices (the architecture of the performance hall, the personal and collective reception/participation devices).

In the years 2000-2020, in addition to artistic experiments which aimed to increase and exceed the canons of cinematographic aesthetics, cinema shows a certain rapprochement with the sphere of video games which have become from 2014 the largest cultural industry on the planet, doubling the business of cinematography. This adds to the collective media that is cinema, the individual dimension applied in social competition through the interactivity of man/machine and man/machine/man-adversary (Vosmeer, M., & Schouten, B., 2014). This process of hybridization of cinematographic narration and video game scriptwriting (Wibowo, T., Deli, D., Syahputra, B., 2024) becomes, in the economic mix of the game and film industries, the cultural policy displayed and followed in many Asian countries, notably in Japan (Otmazgin, N., 2022) and China (Kim, J., 2022).

Faced with these breaks in the genre and these transdisciplinary interpenetrations, cinema itself, with its own dynamics, seeks from 2007 to propose its own solutions which, based on standards already experienced in the past such as IMAX, known since 1971, offering with the transition to “all digital”, from 2009 where digital postproduction represents 70% of films, technological adaptations

widespread across the entire profession. From now on, immersiveness, interactivity, multi-sensory and mixed realities will be at the heart of any innovation affecting film production and distribution.

The appearance of VOD platforms, some of which, like Arte 360° in Europe, are specialized in VR, completes this process on the broadcasting and spectator side.

The architecture of cinema theatres follows this movement, particularly in terms of large immersive 3D theatres with glasses, where we observe in particular the Canadian standard IMAX which at the end of 2015 increased to 1000 screens and in 2017 already equips 1300 theatres in 75 countries, above all in commercial multiplexes (Orzel, C., 2017), thus encouraging the production of numerous specific blockbusters in stereoscopic 3D or with 2D/3D doubling (for example: Dunkirk – 2017, Avatar – The Way of Water – 2022, Oppenheimer – 2023, Dune – 2021 and 2024, Civil War – 2024).

Some of these productions also use “motion capture” technology to “naturalize” 3D animation, a further step towards obtaining and perfecting the effect of mixing realities. This is particularly visible in the case of the Chinese film industry where “motion capture” revives the traditional concept of “suppositionality” (jiadingxing) (Quah Sy, R., 2010) and reinvents itself in “virtual realism” (McGrath, J., 2021).

The other Asian film industries are trying to follow the same path, on the production side and on the architecture side, by focusing not on 3D but on the widening and multiplication of the viewer's visual fields. In 2009 the Asian group CJ 4DPLEX created the 4DX room architecture (adjustable seats, numerous physical effects – vibration, acoustic, olfactory and meteorological) and in 2012 the ScreenX format completed this approach with production and 270° projection distributed over 3 screens and since 2020 with the 4th on the ceiling. Since the first installation in Seoul in South Korea in 2009, these standards have equipped more than 750 theatres in 65 countries, and since 2019 have broadcast around fifteen blockbusters per year, designed exclusively for this format or adapted

(for example: Alita: Battle Angel – 2019, Wonder Woman 1984 – 2020, Spider-Man: No Way Home – 2021, Top Gun: Maverick – 2022, Napoleon – 2023, Furiosa: A Mad Max Saga – 2024).

As we see, already before the digitalization of the profession, but even more after, the propensity for immersion, interactivity, multi-sensoriality and the mix of realities passes from experiments to its expression in the establishment of industrial standards which now guide production, architecture, but also the economy, sociology and culture of cinema.

This trend currently finds its strongest affirmation in the recent extensions of two international film festivals: the Venice Film Festival “Venice Immersive Extended Reality - the XR - Extended Reality section”, with 63 projects in and out of competition in 2024, and of the Cannes Film Festival “The Immersive Competition” with 8 VR productions in the competition, including the work “En amour” by Claire Bardainne, Adrien Mondot and Laurent Bardainne which was exhibited at the Georges Méliès Creative Industries Campus of Côte University d'Azur in Cannes, and 6 works out of competition.

4.3 The immersive dynamics of innovation in contemporary art

By observing different circuits of consecration of art since the 2010s we see that the propensity for immersion, interactivity, multi-sensoriality and the mix of realities is an underlying trend crossing the entire field of art global. It is therefore the predominant factor in the convergence of contemporary art and cinema, presenting the same orientation.

Furthermore, major artists are often cited in both sectors simultaneously, as artists and as filmmakers/videographers. Bil Viola, recently deceased, is part of this class. His work “Autoritratto” from 2013 is currently on display at Galleria degli Uffizi di Firenze. The artist is represented by the slow movie (the special camera powered by Canon) in aquatic immersion, the symbol of what will happen in the evolution of the demonstrative support and the treatment of perceptual space in contemporary art during the following decade.

Today, the 2024 edition of the Biennale di Venezia presents at least 4 major immersive installations, thus consecrating the trend of two reciprocal dynamics of the cinema-art couplet in one of the most important international events.

The Biennale di Venezia 2024 edition also exhibits, in the Maltese pavilion, the work which will undoubtedly be a landmark in the history of 21st century art, "Will Follow the Ship" by Matthew Attard. Here immersion is integrated as constitutive feedback from two sides of the audio-visual work, creation and viewing. Eye-tracking technology is integrated into the construction of the work using Artificial Intelligence which translates the spectator experience into the construction of the work that is projected.

This same experimental technology which is used here as the creative and driving force of the creative process will be at the heart of our future approach within the framework of WP5.3.2 (see the final report of WP5.3.1) where by exploring the relationships between the creative field of cinema and artistic education, we indicate how the strengthening of education in immersion techniques and mixed realities could constitute the decisive asset in the process of increasing the attractiveness of European cinema (Liao, Y., 2023).

It is also with this in mind that the 3 videos and immersive scenarios by Sara Tirelli were created and integrated into the educational process in the two creative master's degree of the UCA.

5 DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

5.1 „43° 43' 23.7972" / 7° 21' 32.3022", VR 360 video, 4K, 5' 15", 2024

Figure 1 “43° 43' 23.7972" / 7° 21' 32.3022", screenshot

“43° 43' 23.7972" / 7° 21' 32.3022" explores the fine line between human and artificial, physical and virtual, real and illusory and it aims to offer an artistic perspective of immersion and reflection on our relationship with reality and technology.

“43° 43' 23.7972" / 7° 21' 32.3022" are the spatial coordinates of the starting point of Nietzsche's ancient path in Eze, traversed by the artist during initial location survey in November 2023. This experience serves as a pivotal inspiration as much as the provocative title of an academic paper "What would Nietzsche have thought of Virtual Reality?" (Botz-Bornstein, T., 2011).

The original idea was to create aerial video footage with a drone to produce a 3D photogrammetric survey of Mont Bastide. However, this type of production proved to not be suitable. This challenge

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did not become an obstacle but rather contributed to the creative definition of the concept, an artistic VR film that would focus on the relationship between Nietzschean nihilism and contemporary digital simulated worlds.

“43° 43′ 23.7972′ / 7° 21′ 32.3022” is VR 360 animation created through Google Earth's satellite visualization system, an immersive film that retraces the path of Nietzsche through a fly-through that challenges our brains not to give in to the illusion of flying.

This work reflects on the theme of illusion, taking the concept of simulation to the extreme and experimenting with contemporary tools of digital creation and storytelling, both visually and textually, and sonically. Starting from Friedrich Nietzsche's quote “The true world is gone” in the chapter “How the ‘true world’ finally became a fable” from *Twilight of the Idols*, the artist has entrusted AI with the creation of an intra psychic dialogue within a virtual space. The result is a surreal inner monologue that explores the relationship between Nietzschean nihilism and virtual reality, a simulated stream of thought that punctuates the rhythm and altitude of the overflight experience. This reasoning, both real and artificial, takes shape through the voice of an actress who does not exist in the physical world, created by a dataset of algorithms. By experimenting with machine learning and AI tools, the artist directed the interpretation of the monologue through a system that simulates the human voice. The AI-generated voice playing an AI generated script is an artistic choice aiming to convey the contrast between real and illusory, between the human deep thought and the void that lies behind the simulated world.

“43° 43′ 23.7972′ / 7° 21′ 32.3022” is an artistic experiment on how contemporary digital tools can simulate human experiences and suggests that while technology can create convincing illusions, it also pushes us to reconsider the nature of authenticity and the evolving relationship between human creativity and artificial intelligence.

5.2 “LOOKING FOR AGNÈS”, VR 360 video, 5K, 4’ 13”, 2024

Figure 2 “LOOKING FOR AGNÈS”, screenshot

“Looking for Agnès” draws inspiration from Agnès Varda's 1958 documentary *Du côté de la côte*, filmed along the French Riviera. This work relocates fragments of the old film into an immersive cinematic space that, stripped of the reassuring perimeter of the frame, the illusion of lenses, and camera movements, manifests as an image-environment imposing a sense of presence.

Under the pretext of retracing the director's gaze, the artist has created a piece that immerses the viewer in the spatiotemporal coordinates that separate traditional cinema from immersive filmmaking. “Looking for Agnès” is a journey through contemporary space where visual traces of a bygone world emerge. It is an exercise in observation and memory, a filmic narrative that is both ironic and melancholic.

The research did not aim for precise adherence to the original framing but sought to create a visual narrative filled with imaginative cues. A travel into Varda's imaginary looking for a visual trace—a

fantastical narrative composed of fragments rediscovered from her production. The artist's choice to leave the presence of the camera visible through the trace of the tripod and sometimes the shadow is a deliberate statement. It underscores the artistic operation at play: the search for a cinematic perspective through the 360 eye of a VR camera.

By repositioning her iconic frames within a contemporary context, the project conveys the overcoming of traditional visual practice. The journey to the locations where Agnès Varda once placed her camera spans various sites in search of landscapes, monuments, and places now inaccessible. It finds its ideal setting on the beaches, where the gaze can reorient itself and find its anchor point at the horizon, where the sky meets the sea. This exploration underscores the transient nature of these spaces, highlighting the tension between past and present, as well as the tension between traditional framing and 360- degree video capture.

In “Looking for Agnès” the juxtaposition of traditional and immersive filmmaking creates a dialogue between two visual eras, encouraging reflection on the evolving nature of cinema.

5.3 “FATHOMING”, VR 360 video, 2’47”, 2024

Figure 3 “FATHOMING”, screenshot

This work represents the second stage of a broader artistic exploration for a project in development called “Fathoming”. In this VR video the verticalization of the gaze delves into the ocean's depths, serving as a definitive liberation from obsolete perspectives. a metaphor for expansion and the pursuit of a new nature. “Fathoming” suggests abandoning the human-built world perspective by staging a plunge beyond the terrestrial surface.

The film begins with a horizon-view and transitions into a free fall into an underwater realm that challenges our perception, inviting the viewer to let go, slow down, and reflect. The absence of a storyline or a guiding voice places the viewer in a unique psychological state, fostering a sense of disorientation and introspection.

The treatment of this work experiments with the body as a unique narrative device, exploring the effects of vertigo and the sensation of free-falling in an aquatic environment. This approach seeks to decouple the viewer from conventional narrative structures, thereby testing a deeper engagement with the medium and its artistic explorations.

In this work, water acts as a medium for cognitive estrangement and a metaphor for the immersive qualities of the medium. The artistic research has focused on the concept of the viewer becoming one with the immersive image, on the fusion of viewer and imagery. As the audience descends into the depths, the boundary between self and environment dissolves, allowing a profound sense of presence.

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6 AESTHETIC AND TECHNICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE DELIVERY

Three immersive audiovisual works that can be viewed with a headset were created by an artist - Sara Tirelli - who followed the instructions of the UCA research team. The aim of these productions was to compare different expressive modes of production, perception and creation. The aim of these videos is to highlight the tensions between emerging and immersive media and traditional cinema. Today's cinema can compete on the basis of innovation in content - narrative or aesthetic - but it can also show a new interest if it innovates in the devices (« dispositifs », Baudry, 1971) and media used to show audiovisual content. These devices are now capable of constituting new symbolic forms capable of creating experiential frameworks that could in time create new or different forms of attraction compared with traditional cinema. More specifically, the three productions identify three points of tension between traditional cinema and immersive vision. Firstly, there is the **reality effect** that the media seem able to reinforce thanks to the 360-degree viewfinder. Secondly, the linear sequentiality of the juxtaposition of shots in film editing is replaced by the **spatialisation of editing**. It is therefore the gaze that will define the limits of the field of vision and therefore also decide the temporality of the events taking place on screen. The consequence of these questions is also the upheaval of the reference points that make up cinematic viewing. This upheaval is linked to the **negation of the boundary between the space of vision and the space of representation** created by the 'an-iconic' status of immersive images: images that deny their frame (Pinotti, 2020). The notion of profilmic - awareness of what we see on the screen - and the linearity of the montage were the hinges of a mode of viewing very quickly naturalised by modern viewers. Immersivity calls this into question: unable to know where to look, viewers can feel lost and must therefore look for new ways to hold on to the sequence.

6.1 Ascension

Immersive media are accompanied by a promise of reality aimed at breaking the frame to bring the viewer into the story, beyond the window. This promise of empathy is linked, on the one hand, to the personification of the viewer's gaze: the video proposes or moves in the direction of an essentially subjective vision (Dalmasso, 2019): incorporation therefore provides a situated point of view where the viewer finds himself bridging the gap between the diegetic world and the space of spectatorial vision. The creative process behind **43° 43' 23.7972' / 7° 21' 32.3022** is an attempt to question the realism promised by the immersive nature of 360° video. This video was made using Google Maps photogrammetry, reproducing an aerial view of the Nietzsche path from the beach at Èze to the village at the top of the hill. 43° 43' 23.7972' / 7° 21' 32.3022 offers an elevation in the air, and therefore an all-encompassing bird's-eye view that is nonetheless based on a Google Maps photogrammetry map: contrasting the realism of video and cinema with photogrammetry.

Firstly, the promise of the reality of visual immersion is linked to a link between the referent - what is actually in front of the camera at the time of filming - and what the viewer sees. 43° 43' 23.7972' / 7° 21' 32.3022 uses a photogrammetric process that seems rigorous but is in fact familiar to the viewer: the Google Maps texture of the Côte d'Azur is thus displayed in all its aesthetic force - an aesthetic pathos reinforced by the many bugs that reveal the presence of the algorithm: the horizon is not flat, the houses turn out to be flattened on the ground, and certain shapes even display the polygons that make them up. Secondly, the promise is linked to a temporality: in the case of immersive film, this temporality most often corresponds to the temporality of vision (fig. 1). The duration of the sequence is in real time, which guarantees that the time of vision corresponds to diegetic time. Even if the duration of the ascent from 43° 43' 23.7972' / 7° 21' 32.3022 corresponds to the duration of the vision, the flat Google map quickly reveals its fixity: the waves do not move, the cars are stopped in an eternal moment. On the contrary, they reveal the artificiality of the visual

substrate and demonstrate the potential for realism offered by immersion based on a totally artificial construction. More precisely, artifice seems to be part of the attraction (from cinema of attractions, Gaudreault, 2008).

6.2 Remediation

Looking for Varda puts Agnès Varda's cinema into tension with 360-degree visions that anachronistically contextualise Varda's cinematographic frames in their real, present-day setting. This process, already seen in other works that bring immersive media into dialogue with traditional cinema (*Rear Window Loop* by Jeff Desom, 2011, for example, or *Montegelato*, 2021, by Davide Rapp) aims to spatialise cinematographic works that are now part of our heritage and imagination. In the case of *Looking for Varda*, we are looking at her second short documentary on the Côte d'Azur (1958), inlaying into the immersive visions 'pieces of the imaginary', like memories of the past of the Côte and of cinema, which are thus spatially superimposed on the immersive vision. Once again, realism is undermined by the presence of the imaginary, which contributes to our perception of the world around us and thus also modifies it with all its pathos and emotional power. Looking for Varda thus exacerbates a difference between two modes of timing: the spatiality of immersive vision contrasts with the linear sequentiality of cinematic vision (Eugeni, 2018). Spatialised forms of editing allow the author to display a new expressive and rhetorical potential, this time based not on linear temporality but rather on the position in a fictional space. Foreground shots suddenly appear, intentionally breaking the viewer's apparent freedom of gaze (fig. 2); images populate the beach at La Croisette or Saint Jean Cap Ferrat, as if the past were always reemerging from the present: like ghosts that we don't usually see but that are always present in these environments. What's more, some sequences 'move' within the immersive image, as if the panoramic could finally dispense with the camera's gaze and wander around the spherical image on its own until it encounters other images and - who knows - almost greets or embraces them (fig. 3).

6.3 “Looking for Agnès” additional interpretation

“Looking for Agnès” is a concrete example of the application of immersive technologies in cinema, exposing the changes and progress made both in technological terms, offering numerous avenues for reflection on the integration of new artistic media in audiovisual productions, and in societal and artistic terms. « Looking for Agnès » explores both the use of new immersive digital technologies and their fusion with traditional media by integrating fragments of Agnès Varda's original film into a cinematic space that encompasses the viewer at 360°: the artist shows how traditional media can be reinvented/ rethought using immersive digital technologies. By fusing so-called 'classic' cinematographic fragments in an immersive environment, Tirelli illustrates how traditional framing and editing techniques can be fused with immersive technologies, demonstrating that the creation of hybrid works is not only technically possible, but also enriches cinematographic language and narrative methods. In particular, this project has given rise to a new methodology for revisiting and recontextualising images that have been captured/extracted/mounted in their initial contexts and spaces. Thanks to 360°, the artist is reinventing the way stories are told and reinventing narrative space by going beyond the constraints of the rectangular frame. 360° places the spectator at the centre of the action, placing greater emphasis on a physical and sensory experience by stimulating the body to move in order to observe and grasp its environment.

From a purely technological and functional point of view, the project highlights innovations in video capture and production, in particular the use of 360° cameras. By deliberately leaving the presence of the camera visible, showing elements such as its shadow and the tripod, the artist underlines the transparency of the creative process and offers an insight into the technical challenges that such a medium engenders: Maintaining a consistent aesthetic in all directions of the 360° view, the absence of off-screen, the reflection of light in space, the reflection of noise and all these aspects imply meticulous planning of the mise-en-scene and attention to detail in all directions in order to create

(or represent) a world in its own right. As a result, 'Looking for Agnès' is a transparent production that explores the limits and potential of immersive media and their hybridisation with conventional media, experimenting with the technical constraints of 360° while offering a comparison, a direct confrontation, of the two mediums (classical and immersive). This exploration is essential for defining the technological objectives to be achieved and for identifying the challenges to be overcome, as well as the opportunities for innovation.

From an artistic point of view, the integration of fragments from Varda's original film offers a hybrid approach that explores new creative processes. This juxtaposition of 'traditional' and immersive images creates multiple creative dialogues. Firstly, a dialogue between cinema's past and its potential future. In short, "Looking for Agnès" is a modern-day Varda. Not only does the artist establish a dialogue between the cinematography of the past, a cinematographic heritage (in both technical and artistic terms), and the cinematography of the future, but also, thanks to 360°, which pushes back the limits of spatiality, establishes a dialogue between two temporalities in the narrative. By integrating fragments of the past into a contemporary setting, Tirelli underlines the ephemeral nature of spaces and the tension between past and present. And more broadly, space is not the only element that has changed, society as a whole has evolved: watching the video, we notice the change in terms of dress, an omnipresence of technique and technology with passers-by holding their smartphones (1: 06 min), the presence of the lift (1:23 min)... Overall, it's a whole society that has adapted to technological progress and gone so far as to adapt spaces to meet new needs and new standards of practicality and comfort. So isn't it time for the cinematographic arts to adapt too? The production confronts the two temporalities both narratively (old images VS new images) and technically (classic images and 360° images).

What's more, the project offers the viewer a new perspective on the way in which cinematographic narratives can be told and shown to an audience: as mentioned above, by using 360° to reinvent

'Du côté de la côte', the project proposes a new way of telling stories and therefore redefines visual storytelling in its entirety, which this time has to take account of the whole space but above all the immersion of the viewer in that space, who is no longer a passive observer but becomes an active participant. This active participation leads us to think of other ways of staging and telling a story when the device no longer allows us to compose the image within a defined framework, in particular by taking into account the spectator's/participant's freedom of movement and therefore freedom of interpretation. From now on, we will have to project a story directly into the space in which it will unfold, taking care to create and arrange a spatio-temporal coherence all around the spectator, which must affect his attention mechanisms as well as his ability to integrate and follow the narrative. It is imperative to give meaning to the audio-visual elements in order to guide the viewer as best they can, who can now live their own experience and therefore understand and memorise the different elements distributed in the space by themselves, without the blinkers of the frame and traditional editing. 'Looking for Agnès' is an introduction to these possibilities: as a 'contemplative' production, viewers can observe the space in which they are immersed by turning their heads or moving their bodies, and this is what is expected of them by placing their gaze at eye level. As he is 'teleported' into the different spaces, sometimes on the beach, sometimes on the Promenade des Anglais, the spectator is invited to explore naturally, and it is thanks to his movements and his innate curiosity that he will be able to notice the incrustations of the past. Tirelli gives the viewer freedom and, almost as a reward, offers them a window on the past that they can explore as if they were travelling through time. And this emotional connection for the viewer, this freedom with the work, is made possible by the new physical interactivity with the environment, which is itself stimulated/enabled by the operator/director. This project bears witness to the artist's desire to enhance the relationship with the viewer by leaving room for his or her process of interpretative construction of the work. The viewer will perceive various elements distributed in the space and will mentally reconstruct the links between the different fragments, then give meaning to the whole, his

or her own interpretation. We give the viewer the creative, emotional and interpretative freedom that they naturally possess when they perceive their natural environment and which they are deprived of with traditional cinematography.

The production explores how immersive technologies can enhance viewer interaction and engagement. As explained above, by creating a sense of presence through active observation of the narrative environment, 'Looking for Agnès' demonstrates how 360° and, more broadly, hybrid cinema can transform the relationship between film and viewer. And it is in this sense that the project serves not only as an example but also as an educational tool to train tomorrow's young creatives in the possibilities offered by immersive media and how immersive technologies can be used to reinvent film-making. To support this, we can draw a parallel with the studies carried out on the cognitive capacities of contemporary spectators (WP5.3.1). The study highlighted the differences between a so-called "creative" audience, which had been introduced to immersive digital technologies (or mixed reality technologies), and a "non-creative" audience. The main differences manifested themselves in better observation and comprehension skills (narrative and emotional) on the part of the 'creatives' faced with these new creative formats. The study was able to suggest a relationship between viewers' familiarity with new types of content and perception, memorisation and comprehension, which would therefore imply learning and adaptation both to new devices and to new types of content and scripting. With this in mind, the creation of a hybrid immersive experience such as 'Looking for Agnès' makes sense insofar as, in the first instance, the project encourages experimentation and innovation.

Although cinema has always been a reflection of society and a driving force behind technical innovation, the industry is nonetheless punctuated by standards that evolve according to the industry's competitiveness and the public's acceptance of these innovations. Laurent Creton in 'Economie du Cinéma. Perspectives stratégiques' (2020) explains that innovative offerings must not

offend audiences, even though their absence can lead to boredom and satiety. Tomorrow's audiences are digital natives. Born with the web and telecommunications, digital natives are accustomed to interactivity, which is omnipresent in many of the audiovisual formats they consume and which have become increasingly popular over the last twenty years: Video games, Twitch, Tik Tok, Reels, Youtube, etc. - viewers of this content can interact with both the content and the device (touch screen, controller, VR headset, etc.). It is therefore essential that ICT (Information and Communication Technology) designers take this need for interactivity into account when designing tools and creating content that make this interaction possible. If there is an interdependence between the evolution of media and the cognitive needs of society, the European film landscape must be able to evolve in order to play a leading role and boost the industry's international competitiveness by looking to the horizon. "Looking for Agnès" is a perfect illustration of this approach, as it incorporates digital and immersive technological innovation and this new need for interactivity, while incorporating a base, an anchor, to avoid offending the audience.

Secondly, the project can contribute to the training of future young professionals in today's film industry, guiding them more towards a mix of creative media. Earlier, we explained that the cognitive capacities of creative people are more highly developed than those of non-creative people. As a result, if non-creative audiences are also to develop an interest in and cognitive capacities for these new formats (and thus become future audiences or future creators), we need to do more to educate them and expose them to immersive digital innovations and new forms of scriptwriting.

The hybridization of classic immersive formats in the manner of "Looking for Agnès" therefore appears to be the best way of getting audiences to accept these innovations, which they will be able to integrate as they become accustomed to them. Creating more hybrid content will first of all standardise the changes and then encourage audiences to adopt them. Furthermore, showing

young filmmakers new forms of artistic and creative expression could encourage them to explore their own creativity through these new formats.

6.4 Diving

The aim of *Fathoming* is to make viewers lose the traditional reference points they use to perceive and make sense of moving images. *Fathoming* plunges the viewer into the unknown by disrupting the essential elements that define cinematic perception. Firstly, verticality is opposed to the horizontality of the cinematic gaze. Instead of offering horizontal panoramas - the type of movement favoured in cinema because of the way the eyes are positioned on the human face - *Fathoming* focuses on the vertical axis, offering a dive into the abyss at night, into a digitally reconstructed sea that is reminiscent of the artificial paper seas in Federico Fellini's *Casanova* (fig. 4). The computer-graphic reconstruction shows how realism gives way to an artificial mise-en-scène, developing the theme initiated by $43^{\circ} 43' 23.7972'' / 7^{\circ} 21' 32.3022''$. Western visual representations are based on two modes of perception. The first is perspective, which originated in Renaissance art. Perspective opens up a mode of focusing that sees the viewer's gaze as the starting point for all narrative visualisation. The spectator is at the centre of the scene – she/he is even its condition of possibility - and she/he determines the narrative value of everything he sees. Cinema altered this primacy of the subjective gaze with the invention of « découpage » by Hollywood cinema, which fragmented the linearity of a sequence and thus defined a new hierarchy of values. In this way, montage became the new focus of narrative values. The immersive image shatters this primacy by placing the spectator back at the heart of the vision: incorporation leads the viewer's gaze to become the centre of the action and to break the frame, at least metaphorically. "The dictatorship of the frame", as Alejandro Inarritu defined it when presenting his immersive work *Carne y Arena* in 2017. Without a frame, however, we also lose the reference points that allow us to make sense of what surrounds us. *Fathoming's* dive leaves us in a smooth space in a kind of abyss that plunges into darkness. It

is in a digital sea - reconstructed in 3D - that the viewer seems to lose himself in the end. The passivity of the cinematic spectator and the separation between the space of the stage and the space of vision had often been called into question by nineteenth-century theories (Duhamel, 1931; Benjamin, 1939; Debord, 1967) and interactivity was presented as a 'myth' at the beginning of the century (Manovich, 2001). Today, a new form of audiovisual representation seems to take place : immersivity. However, *Fathoming* reminds us that the potential for action enabled by immersive technologies plunges us into the unknown: without a clear frame we have no landmark to know where to really go.

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6.5 Student production n°1 – “Château de la Napoule / Napoule Art Foundation”

Figure 4 “Château de la Napoule / Napoule Art Foundation”, screenshot

Link to the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jFchzIQPNs>

To watch in the Virtual Reality headset. If you are viewing on the computer's flat screen, please set the quality to higher (1080s ^{HD} or 2160s ^{4K}).

This video was produced before the plenary meeting of the REBOOT consortium on May 14-16, 2024, at the Château de la Napoule / Napoule Art Foundation during the Cannes Film Festival.

On this occasion, the members of the consortium received an immersive video produced by MAPIC Master students (HIC Mention) one week before their arrival.

The immersive scenario had to achieve two objectives:

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- Provide condensed information on the heritage site, its history and its current cultural functioning, according to the rules of classic film narration.
- Facilitate the spatial orientation of the viewer who in turn will become an actor in his own exploration, first during the active (enactive) viewing of the 360° video and then during the visit to the real building.

Our hypothesis is that a feedback loop is established between VR viewing and the actual visit. The first facilitates the second, and in return the real visit encourages us to revisit the immersive video and fully exploit its visual and audio resources. According to the testimonies received, some people who first viewed the video on the flat screen of their personal computer, after the actual visit rewatched the video in a virtual reality headset, making the most of the ergonomics of the media.

6.6 Student production n°2 – “Two parallel scenes with reciprocal causality of action”

Figure 5 “Space 1 with space 2 inlay”, screenshot

Link to the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dvO5QGbyiM>

Figure 6 “Space 2 with space 1 inlay”, screenshot

Link to the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bCiDqvtk6Bo>

Cognitive tests: viewing two parallel scenes with reciprocal causality of action in the natural environment and in the VR environment.

The experience system is made up of two communicating spaces, each presenting an opening so that we can preview the neighbouring space, reciprocally.

In each of the spaces we perform a fragment of a theatrical distributed over two communicating rooms and whose simultaneous actions influence each other.

The first group of different viewers was invited to directly view the two scenes, with the possibility of moving around to see sometimes one space, sometimes the other.

Both scenes were filmed in 360° simultaneously.

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Three informative videos and immersive scenarios

The second group of different viewers was invited to watch a scene with the insertion of a view of the neighbouring stage. Each time the view of the adjacent scene was of interest for understanding the action played by the actors, the spectators had the possibility of concentrating on the incrustation of this neighbouring scene. The behaviours attesting to this interest were recorded and interpreted. The experimental device will then be augmented with the possibility of “teleporting” into the two scenes reciprocally in order to analyse the management of attentional points of different spectators.

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